

The Effect of Business Motivation and Discipline in the Performance of Women Entrepreneurs

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Abstract: One solution to solve the problem of unemployment is to try to create their own jobs through the path of entrepreneurship. Based on these facts, entrepreneurship (entrepreneurship) will have a very important role for the people of Indonesia, especially in addressing the problem of unemployment. Entrepreneurship is one of the Indonesian economic driving progresses. It is not only conducted by the men, women too. Nowadays, women entrepreneur were minority, but entrepreneurship in some country cannot be separated from the participant and role of women. The role was from micro, small, and medium enterprises (UMKM) such as a grocery store. The goal of this research is to analyze the business motivation and discipline of entrepreneurial women in relation to business performance. The methodology research uses SPSS 24 measurements and the results of the research shows that business motivation and discipline have a positive effect on business performance

Keywords: Motivation, Discipline, performance, Traders and entrepreneurs, women

I. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, the existence of entrepreneurs is very important and has a large contribution to the Indonesian economy. This role is assisted by the existence of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) that can save Indonesia from adversity. MSMEs entrepreneurs are the foundation for economic development in Indonesia. Micro, small and medium entrepreneurs become the motor of innovation and national development because they can open jobs, provide national goods and services and contribute to GDP and eradicate poverty and increase family welfare so that its existence is considered very important.

The development of entrepreneurship is still dominated by men. This is because historically entrepreneurship is an area of power for men (Casson et al., 2006). The same thing was also expressed by Davidson and Burke (2004) which stated that women entrepreneurs were still a minority among entrepreneurs. The reason why women entrepreneurs are still a minority is the obstacles faced by women entrepreneurs in starting or running a business.

World Bank (2011) states that in almost all countries, women are more likely to engage in low productivity activities than men. As a result of these differences in women's and men's employment, there is a gap in income in all forms of economic activity, such as agriculture, entrepreneurship, and manufacturing.

One economic actor who has a considerable influence on the development of MSME is an entrepreneurial woman. According to Tambunan (2012), MSMEs in both developing and poor countries, including Indonesia, many women undertake economic activities outside the home such as becoming small traders, stall owners, or helping husbands manage household businesses solely to increase family income. The participation of women entrepreneurs in economic growth is very important, not only to reduce poverty levels among women, but also as an important step towards increasing household income and encouraging overall economic development of the country. At present, the role of women as micro, small and medium enterprises in the Indonesian economy is gradually increasing the people's economy. SME ownership data shows that as much as 60 percent of micro-businesses are managed by women who are energy for economic development.

The existence of women entrepreneurs in Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) is the reality of the economic life of most Indonesian people. The role of women as micro entrepreneurs in the Indonesian economy gradually turned out to be increasingly improving the people's economy. Therefore, the opportunity to improve MSMEs

is through contributions from women entrepreneurs. One of the MSMEs that are in great demand by women entrepreneurs is the trading business. Usually those traded in grocery stalls and markets are groceries and household necessities.

One market that is the object of research by the author is the Cikini market in Central Jakarta. This market was founded in 1962, this market had become a shopping place for the elite Menteng, Central Jakarta during the reign of the governor of DKI Soemarno. From the observations, many factors that influence why women's entrepreneurial business performance often does not progress are there is no education and training about entrepreneurship, decreased trading motivation, do not want to take risks in terms of selling new products, no venture capital, and no government policies to improve the performance of women-based trade entrepreneurs.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

Motivation

A person's productivity is largely determined by the "mental virus" that is in him. Mental virus is a mental condition that drives a person to be able to achieve maximum achievement. mental virus referred to as Achievement Motivation. (Mangkunegara 2010). According to Hasibuan (2003) motivation comes from the Latin word movere which means drive or driving force. In providing motivation agencies have the same goals, there are several goals that can be obtained, among others, improve employee morale and job satisfaction, improve employee work performance, create a good atmosphere and working relationships, increase loyalty, creativity and participation, increase the level of employee welfare and increase the sense of employee responsibilities towards duties.

Motivation is the process that begins with the need for someone to be stimulated by something. which is beyond the individual self and subsequently towards the goal or the goal that has already been achieved determined (Soelton, 2016). Motivation can be interpreted as an impulse in a person to do or do a business activity or task as well as possible in order to achieve achievements with honors and business profits.

Discipline

According to SoengengPridjominto, (2011) argues, discipline is a condition that is created and formed through a process of a series of behaviors that demonstrate the values of obedience, obedience, orderliness, and order ". Because it is integrated with him, then the attitude or action that is done is no longer or no longer felt as a burden, on the contrary it will burden him when he does not do. Values of obedience have become a part of behavior in their lives. Such attitudes and behaviors are created through the fostering process through family, education, and experience or recognition of the example of their environment. Discipline will make him know what distinguishes things that should be done that must be done, which can be done, which should not be done.

According to Hasibuan (2007) stated that discipline is the awareness and willingness of a person to obey all company regulations and social norms that apply. Based on the theory above, discipline is the attitude of someone who voluntarily and consciously obeys all the rules and aware of their duties and responsibilities. So, he will obey or do all his duties properly, not by force. With this explanation, it is needed for an entrepreneurial company or company in relation to facilitate and expedite the company in achieving its objectives, because the discipline that is embedded in every employee or owner of the company will provide their willingness to obey and run the rules that have been set in order to advance the company.

Business Performance

According to Stoner (1995), that performance is a function of motivation, skills, and role perception. Meanwhile, according to Bernardin and Russel (1993) defining performance is "Performance is the record of outcomes produced on a specified job function or activity during a specified time period". Performance is the work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in order to achieve organizational goals in a certain period of time. (PrawiroSuntoro in Pabundu, 2011). According to Gibson (2013), performance refers to the level of success in carrying out tasks as well as the ability to achieve the goals set. Performance is stated as good and successful if the desired goals can be achieved properly.

According to Jauch and Glueck (1988) business performance is seen from the level of sales, the level of profit, return on capital, the level of turnover and the market share it achieves. Based on the above theory, performance is the

ability of a company to achieve corporate goals effectively and efficiently with good judgment. Performance is the real behavior that is displayed and each person matches his role in the company (Parashakti,2018)

According to Sugiyono (2013), the hypothesis is a temporary answer to the research problem formulation. The purpose of doing a hypothesis is to find out how much will be done in solving certain problems. Based on the analysis framework above:

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Framework

H1: Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Business Performance.

H2: Discipline has a positive and significant effect on Business Performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODE

In this study using two methods of data analysis namely descriptive analysis and inferential analysis.

Descriptive Analysis Method

According to Sugiyono (2012) Descriptive method is a method used to analyze data by describing or describing data that has been collected as it is without intending to make conclusions that apply to the public or generalization. In this case the writer will analyze the data that will relate to the motivation and discipline.

Inferential Analysis Method

In this method, the authors test and estimate the variables that are the focus of the research, motivation and discipline (as the independent variable) and business performance (as the dependent variable).

In this study the authors used multiple analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis is a method of analysis used to determine the accuracy of predictions of the influence that occurs between the independent variable (X) against the dependent variable (Y). The formula for multiple linear regression is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

y = Business Performance

a = Constant

x₁ = Motivation

x₂ = Discipline

e = Standard Estimation Error

IV. RESULT

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is a form of analysis that discusses the extent of the influence of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) using linear equations. Where for the variable (X1) is motivation, and (X2) Discipline where (Y) is performance. In calculating the regression coefficient in this study the authors used the SPSS version 24 program.

Tabel 4.1

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error
1 (Constant)	10.164	3.903
M	.173	.065
S	.228	.079

a. Dependent Variable: Business Performance

b. M = motivation, S = Discipline

Based on table 4.1 about the coefficient of multiple linear regression correlation, it can be seen that the linear regression equation is:

$$Y = 10,164 + 0,173 x_1 + 0,228 x_2$$

Information:

Y = Performance

X1 = Motivation

X2 = Discipline

Based on table 4.1 it can be explained that the results of multiple linear regression coefficients showing a constant value of 10,164 mathematically states that if the value of the motivational variable (X1), and Discipline (X2), equals zero (0) then the value of Y is 10.164.

1) Motivation (X1) has a regression coefficient of 0.173 if the motivational variable increases by 1% performance will increase by 0.173 where other variables are fixed.

2) Discipline (X2) has a regression coefficient of 0.228, if the discipline variable increases by 1% then the performance will increase by 0.228 where other variables are fixed. This means that the variable of discipline has a positive and significant effect on the performance variable (Y).

F - Test

The F test is used to test the significant regression together ie whether the independent variable has an influence on the dependent variable. Hypothesis testing between motivation and discipline on employee performance can be used by using the F test by comparing the F arithmetic and F tables.

Tabel 1.2

F Test

ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	693.848	3	231.283	13.708	.000 ^a
Residual	1855.907	110	16.872		
Total	2549.754	113			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, Discipline

b. Dependent Variable: Business Performance

From table 1.it is explained that the F value indicates (13,708 > 2.80) with a significant value of 0,000 < 0.05 = Ho is rejected. This means that motivation and discipline have a positive and significant effect on performance

T- Test

T test is used to determine whether partially motivation and discipline variables have a positive relationship with performance. Based on the significance value of the SPSS output results:

Tabel 1.

T - Test

Coefficients^a

Model	Standardized Coefficients			
		Beta	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)			2.604	.010
Motivation	.220		2.661	.009
Discipline	.238		2.604	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Business Performance

b. M : motivation, D: Discipline

Based on Table 1.it is concluded that the results of the t test are as follows .:

- 1) The motivation variable (X1) has at arithmetic of 2.661 with a significant level of 0.009. While the value of t table with df114 and a significant level of 5% obtained a value of 1981, then motivation has a positive and significant effect on k performance, this is according to the hypothesis used.
- 2) The discipline variable (X2) has at arithmetic of 2,881 with a significant level of 0.005. While the value of t table with df114 and a 5% significance level was obtained for 1,981. Then discipline has a positive and significant effect on the performance of this matter according to the hypothesis used. The hypothesis test that is conducted concludes the result as follows.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study the author can be concluded as follows: Motivation has a positive effect on the business performance of women entrepreneurs. The need to increase motivation in efforts to improve performance and Discipline has a positive and significant effect on business performance. Discipline will affect performance improvement.

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